

Magnetic Study of Uranyl Complexes of some Schiff Bases

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URANYL complexes of Schiff bases obtained by condensing salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehyde with aromatic amines, like 2-aminopyridine, aniline and nitroanilines, have been isolated and characterised. The complexes have the formula ML_2 and $M(LH)_2(NO_3)_2$ where $M = UO_2$ and L and LH = Schiff base. The magnetic susceptibility values of all the ligands and their complexes have been compared with the computed ones, obtained by adding the experimental molar susceptibilities of the components, assuming strict additivity. The percentage deviations between the observed and the computed values clearly show that they are outside the experimental error, and therefore are significant. These deviations have been discussed in the light of Van Vleck's equation for the molar susceptibility of polyatomic molecule.

Experimental

Magnetic susceptibilities of the uranyl complexes were measured by a modified form of Gouy's balance, described by Prasad *et al.*¹. The values of specific susceptibility (χ) and molar susceptibility (χ_m) of uranyl complexes were determined. The molar magnetic susceptibilities were then computed using Pascal's additivity law. The computed values were found to be higher than the experimental values. This deviation from Pascal's law is regarded as a measure of ligand field strength in terms of χ_p values. The calculated percentage-deviation values are reported in Table 1.

Discussion

It is evident from the results that all the complexes are diamagnetic. This indicates that all of them

are spin-paired complexes of hexavalent uranium. Assuming the Pascal's additivity law, molar magnetic susceptibilities of all these complexes were computed. The computed values are found to be higher than the experimental values (Table 1). These deviations are beyond the experimental error and therefore are significant.

According to Van Vleck², the susceptibility of a polyatomic molecule without a resultant spin is given by the equation,

$$\chi_m = \chi_a + \chi_p$$

where, χ_a represents the diamagnetic term and is a function of $\sum \frac{1}{r^n}$ (the radius of all electronic orbits in the molecule), and χ_p represents the second order paramagnetism, independent of temperature, arising on account of the mixing of the ground and excited states of electrons in the molecule. If the metal-nitrogen-bond in the complex is sufficiently strong, the associating units will come very close to the metal atom, thus decreasing the value of $\sum \frac{1}{r^n}$ and hence that of the diamagnetic susceptibility of the molecule.

Freed and Kasper³ and Lawrence⁴ have observed that χ_p term is definitely present in uranyl complexes. Van Vleck² attributed this paramagnetism to the matrix elements of the magnetic moment operator $\beta(L+2S)$ between the ground state and higher states. The contribution from the spin magnetic moment is zero since all spins are paired off in the ground state. As the largest orbital contribution comes from the two $5f\sigma$ bonding electrons, Eisenstein and Pryce⁵ have assumed that f -electrons are responsible for the magnetism of the uranyl ion. Belford and Belford^{6,7} have shown, from the orbital overlap integral calculations, that the $5f\sigma$ uranium orbitals do not overlap much with the oxygen orbitals as the $6d$ orbitals do, and that considerable π bonding also might be involved.

Since the nature of various ligands complexing with the uranyl ion, are similar in structure, it is concluded that comparison of χ_p values will be possible. Examination of results show that the χ_p

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF URANYL COMPLEXES OF SOME SCHIFF BASES

Compd.	Mol. weight	χ	χ_m (observed)	χ'_m (computed)	$\Delta\chi_m = (\chi_m - \chi'_m) = (\chi_p)$	% $\Delta\chi_m$
$[UO_2(C_{12}H_{11}ON)_2](NO_3)_2$ (Salicylanil)	788	0.217 8	171.62	210.18	-38.56	-22.46
$[UO_2(C_{14}H_{13}ON)_2](NO_3)_2$ (<i>p</i> -Methylsalicylanil)	816	0.229 5	187.27	233.66	-46.39	-24.77
$[UO_2(C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2)_2](NO_3)_2$ (<i>m</i> '-Nitrosalicylanil)	878	0.198 8	174.10	216.88	-42.78	-24.57
$[UO_2(C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2)_2](NO_3)_2$ (<i>p</i> '-Nitrosalicylanil)	878	0.197 4	173.31	216.70	-43.39	-25.03
$[UO_2(C_{12}H_9ON_2)_2]$ (Salicylidene-2-iminopyridine)	664	0.158 8	105.11	156.60	-51.49	-48.98
$[UO_2(C_{12}H_{11}ON_2)_2]$ (<i>p</i> -Methylsalicylidene-2-iminopyridine)	692	0.176 4	122.06	180.16	-58.10	-47.59

value varies with the nature of the ligand. Considering the temperature independent paramagnetism χ_p term as a measure of ligand field strength, the following order of ligand field strength has been established: salicylanil $>$ *m'*-nitrosalicylanil $>$ *p*-methylsalicylanil $>$ *p'*-nitrosalicylanil $>$ *p*-methylsalicylidene-2-iminopyridine $>$ salicylidene-2-iminopyridine.

An attempt has been made to examine the magnetic susceptibility values of isomeric substituted complexes. The values of χ_m suggest that introduction of substituent in salicylanil (in the salicylaldehyde ring as well as in the amine ring) in various positions causes an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility value. Langevin's theory postulates that a decrease in the effective positive charge will result in an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility. An order of increase in the susceptibility values as a result of substitution of different groups at isomeric positions is represented as follows: salicylanil $<$ *p*-methylsalicylanil; salicylanil $<$ *p'*-nitrosalicylanil $<$ *m'*-nitrosalicylanil; salicylidene-2-iminopyridine $<$ *p*-methylsalicylidene-2-iminopyridine.

According to French⁸, if the substituent is *ortho-para* directing, the *ortho* compound should have higher susceptibility than either *meta* or *para* compound, while when the substituent is *meta* directing, the compound has the highest susceptibility values than the other substituents. This difference is attributed to the presence of higher electron density at *ortho* position in compounds containing two-electron repelling groups *ortho* to each other, and in *meta* compound to a higher electron density at *meta* position when the two groups are *meta* to each other. The order indicates that the authors findings are in partial agreement with the above findings.

Percentage deviation and symmetry of the molecule: In the Schiff base complexes studied, coordination occurs through nitrogen⁹⁻¹² and that the bonds involved are of coordinate covalent type. These bonds are likely to cause contraction of the electronic orbits whereby value of $\sum \bar{r}^2$ of the molecule is decreased. Since diamagnetic susceptibility is a radical function, the decrease in the value of $\sum \bar{r}^2$ would lower the diamagnetic susceptibility of complex molecule. This view is supported by the negative deviations observed by the authors.

It is thus clear that the observed deviations from additivity may be due to the changes in the χ_d term of Van Vleck equation. Further, since the bond between component molecule is strong, it is likely to bring about a change in symmetry of the component molecule. χ_p term, which is also dependent on the symmetry of the molecule, is likely to be affected due to this type of bonding. Thus the observed deviation from additivity may be on account of the changes in terms χ_d and χ_p both. The deviation is therefore

the net result of the two opposing effects χ_d and χ_p having opposite signs. Since, the symmetry of complex formed may be entirely different from that of the constituent molecule, the change in the χ_p term would obviously be more significant.

It appears that the χ_p term is more significant in bringing about a change in the molar susceptibility of the complex. This term is dependent on the symmetry of the molecule; and hence, greater the symmetry of the molecule, the smaller will be its contribution to χ_m in the Van Vleck's equation. It is therefore expected that greater the symmetry of the molecule, smaller will be the deviation¹³ from additivity and vice-versa. Hence, all the complexes reported in this investigation appeared to be distorted.

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Thioarsenites of Less-common Metals. Electro-metric Investigations on the Composition of Uranyl Thioarsenites as a Function of pH

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THE composition of heavy metal arsenites precipitated by the addition of sodium arsenite solutions to heavy metal salts is governed mainly by pH. The investigation of these compounds is difficult because of the adsorption of arsenic oxide by metallic hydroxides; the conversion of orthoarsenite to pyro- and meta-arsenite takes place with great ease, and these dissolve in excess of alkali and acid¹. Consequently, analytical methods have failed to give a correct view of their composition.